

A Review Study of Application on Electrical Automation in Electrical Engineering

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The use of a series of devices with automatic detection and control functions to realize real-time or remote control, management, and monitoring of the original electrical system is known as automation in electrical engineering. As a result, electrical automation technology has a lot of room for development in the field of electrical engineering, and it's worth looking into for electrical installation engineering and scientific research departments. It is necessary to optimize the production mode, reduce costs, and maintain the good working performance of electrical equipment in the actual manufacturing process. As a result, this article examines the application of electrical automation in electrical engineering briefly in the hopes of providing a useful reference.

Keywords: ELECTRICAL AUTOMATION; ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING; APPLICATION

1. Introduction

In terms of electrical engineering, the centralized process of all system functions is handled by the same processor. As a result, the processor is under a great deal of stress and strain, which reduces its efficiency. And the number of service objects for electrical equipment monitoring is so large that the host must bear a significant burden, necessitating the use of more cables, resulting in an increase in investment costs. Furthermore, the introduction of long-distance cable will have a direct impact on the power system's reliability and stability. A malfunction is more likely to occur when it operates under high load for an extended period of time. As a result, in the application of automation technology in electrical engineering, the concept of centralized monitoring is the most widely used.

The use of remoting can not only reduce the use of cable, but it can also save money on investment and improve security and stability. However, because this design improves electrical communication, it is frequently used in smaller electrical engineering. Basic automation control is shown in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Basic Automation Control

Network technology and computer technology are becoming more widely used as the information age progresses. Field bus is an example of network technology, and its implementation can significantly improve the system's targeted design. It can also adopt different functions depending on the interval, allowing it to meet the actual requirements. The concept of field bus can reduce equipment spacing, analog quantity, and terminal cabinet based on the benefits of remoting. As a result, this method is widely used in the field of electrical engineering, and it is expected to become the future trend in electrical automation development.

2. Directions of application

2.1 Protection

In the field of integrated automation, the strength of experimental research has advanced to an advanced level. At the same time, its global leadership in the field of intelligent automation technology protection is undeniable. The hierarchical integrated automation device is appropriate for power stations with varying voltage levels. The latest network communication, artificial intelligence, integrated automatic control theory, adaptive theories, computer new technology, and so on are used in the electric automatic protection device. A new study was conducted on the automatic protection principle of an electrical system in order to continuously improve its level of safety, resulting in a new protection device with the advantage of intelligent control.

2.2 Distributed networks

The automation technology distribution network follows the public information model, which is the internationally recognized minimum standard. The transmission network uses a theoretical algorithm that combines practical operation with cutting-edge software. The calculation is completed in the final process of power flow calculation by incorporating gray neuron algorithms for artificial intelligence into the load forecasting process and using recursive virtual-flow algorithms of the distribution network. Advanced application software, information distribution network integration, medium and low voltage network digital, and distribution network model are some of the major breakthroughs in distribution network automation technology in the distribution system, which have effectively solved the carrier in the distribution network of the decline, routing, and other technical problems. The sensitivity of carrier receiving and receiving has improved largely due to the use of digital signal processing technology.

2.3 Artificial intelligence

For practical application research on the aspects of evolutionary theory, expert systems, and fuzzy logic, design planning, operation analysis, and fault diagnosis of power systems and their components are carried out. The intelligent control and application of power systems are investigated in conjunction with the development needs of relevant enterprises. The operation of the power system and the level of intelligent control are improved as a result of studying the above practical software.

3. Applications

3.1 PLC technology

PLC technology refers to the use of simple programming to control working links. Programming does not have a lot of requirements. Ordinary technicians can control through programming if they understand the objects and the control requirements. PLC technology stands out for its ease of use, simple programming, powerful functions, and adaptability to a variety of working environments, and lower cost than similar technologies. This demonstrates that PLC technology has a low entry barrier and a broad range of applications. As a result, it is widely used in a variety of work environments. Electrical automation replaces the original controller with PLC technology in order to lower costs, increase efficiency, and achieve high-quality electrical automation work. The Basic PLC Design Board is shown in Figure 1.2.

It is necessary to pay attention to the programming when using PLC technology. The program is the most important factor in allowing PLC technology to play its own role. Any errors in the program will have a significant impact on electrical automation, as well as the stable operation of electrical engineering.

Figure 1.2: PLC Board Design

3.2 Energy conservation

Whether or not energy-saving and monitoring issues in electrical engineering construction can be effectively addressed is determined by the cost and benefit of production. The use of electrical automation must be strengthened in order to achieve effective energy savings and monitoring in power plants involved in the development of electrical engineering. The introduction of electrical automation can analyze the energy consumption status of the power plant's equipment and circuits, and then devise an effective working plan to ensure that the energy-saving idea is reflected throughout the power plant's production practice, ensuring good environmental protection benefits while increasing its economic benefit. The introduction of electrical automation can perfect the service function of the monitoring system, enhance the control effect in the running process of the system, realize the integrated use of monitoring information, and real-time monitoring of the power plant's production process, based on the actual requirements for decentralized monitoring in the production process of the power plant. In addition, monitoring devices based on electrical automation can acquire information on the operation of the power plant's production equipment, making maintenance easier.

3.3 Power grid

The automatic power plant's point channel, the station end, and the control center make up the power grid dispatching system. The power grid dispatching workstation, large screen display, and central server are the primary components involved. The power plant, the power grid dispatching center, and the terminal substation can all be connected to the power system's local area network for monitoring purposes. Furthermore, automation technology used in electrical engineering can monitor the working condition of the power grid at any time, allowing for real-time data collection and confirmation, as well as confirming whether the power system can load the current power consumption based on data analysis, allowing for true automatic

power grid dispatching. As a result, it is required to increase the use of electrical automation and related technologies, improve dispatching, and assure the power system's reliability.

3.4 Distributed network

Electrical automation is crucial in the distribution system. To boost the favorable effects of electrical automation, its application size must be expanded. Currently, the use of electrical automation in distribution systems can be divided into three categories: distribution automation with centralized monitoring, distribution automation with a combination of centralized monitoring and distribution management, and distribution automation with local control, with the first two being the most popular. Both of them use a distributed structure to provide time unification and a reliable connection between the substation and the master station, resulting in a highly centralized distribution automation system. The use of electrical automation in distribution systems can help to arrange power information in a logical and rational way, carry out efficient and accurate distribution work, and increase power supply dependability and overall electrical engineering efficiency.

4. Advantages

4.1 Controllability

Breakthroughs in the power sector and power automation technologies have been made in as a result of the country's continued development and success in social economics, science, and technology. The dependence of automation technology on the development of various industries is likewise increasing stronger and stronger as the development of modern cities accelerates. As a result, electrical automation technology is gaining in importance. With the growing popularity of electricity, people are placing greater demands on the controllability of electrical automation technologies. Electrical automation technology may gather a lot of peripheral information because it is a vital critical connection in the power system. These data must be processed to create an information control management system with high controllability, which increases electrical automation technology's controllability and makes the system more stable. Improving the controllability of electrical automation can help power industry grow while simultaneously improving the safety and stability of power system operations.

4.2 Protection

Various elements, such as the complexity of the surroundings, the diversification of equipment, or the non-standard connection of the power supply line, have an impact on the operation of the electric power system. As a result, equipment failure and a circuit fault are likely to occur. Traditional manual monitoring and overhaul are unable to completely comprehend the working state of the equipment, posing a number of possible safety risks. Electrical automation control technology can safely turn off the power, terminate the

operational procedure, eliminate safety mishaps and financial losses, and ensure the safe operation of electrical equipment when equipment breaks down or the circuit becomes unstable.

4.3 Integration

Automation technology, which is widely employed in a variety of industries and sectors, obtains a very good result. However, because the automation technology process flow is complex, technical researchers optimize and improve it in order to increase the use of automation technology in a variety of industries. The most noticeable difference is the simplification of electrical control, measurement, and power protection interconnections, among other things. Electrical automation technology optimization and improvement not only improves the quality and efficiency of electrical enterprises' production, but it also effectively reduces the workload of manual production, lowering the error rate of technical operations in the manual production process and, to a degree, lowering the risk of safety accidents in the process.

4.4 Production development

The integration of the benefits of information technology and computer networks in the development of electrical automation is critical to the improvement of the production level of electrical engineering practice. More particularly, the electrical engineering equipment performance supported by electrical automation may be continuously enhanced, hence improving the operating stability of electrical equipment and the production level of electrical engineering practice; The production mode of electrical engineering supported by electrical automation can be optimized to provide scientific guidance for the safe implementation of production plans and to continuously raise production levels; in the production practice of electrical engineering supported by electrical automation, the occurrence rate of problems is reduced, resulting in excellent productivity.

5. Future & practical application

5.1 Smart grid

One of the most extensively utilized technologies in computer technology is the use of information management systems. Smart grid technology will be formed by combining computer technology and electrical automation technology to create an intelligent control technology for the entire grid. Power generation, transmission and transformation, dispatching, distribution, user and other links are all covered by smart grid technologies. In the computer technology system, the stability control system and the substation automation system are frequently employed. It can be considered a prototype of the current smart grid in certain ways, and it also sets the groundwork for smart grid construction in . In the construction process, communication technology, as a representative of smart grid, must rely on a large number of computer technologies. As a result, it is required to have the qualities of dependability, directionality, and real-time.

This system requires modern advanced network communication technology, and its existence is entirely reliant on computer technology, therefore it also functions as an information management system.

5.2 Openness

Opening is a basic technique that can be utilized to achieve dispatching automation, and it is an unavoidable trend. With the network acting as the carrier, the electrical automation structure and the external interface can be linked to form the power system movement technology. Electrical automation technology can integrate the advantages of computers and simulation technology, establish an open technology structure, and meet the application needs of various fields in terms of equipment design and manufacturing, allowing information technology to provide technical support for the development of electrical automation and play a practical role.

5.3 Substations

To some extent, the realization of substation automation is dependent on the advancement of computer technology. Substation automation, which is the most significant and crucial vital link in the modernization of power production, is required. Computer technology is used to realize substation automation. The computer is fully exploited in this process to achieve digitization, networking, and secondary equipment integration. It is the signal cable that totally substitutes the computer's optical fiber or power wire. The computer screen, as well as the automation record statistics and movement management, are all achieved by substation automation. It also involves the operation and monitoring. The upgrading of so many components is the reason for the substation automation's success. Transformer substations and associated transmission and distribution lines are required to ease the connection between power users and power plants. The automatic management of substations is achieved not only to form dispatching automation, but also to satisfy the needs of various substation operations.

5.4 PLC technology

PLC technology can handle all aspects of data collection, analysis, and processing, as well as table checking, sorting, data conversion, computing, bit manipulation, and data delivery. The collected and processed data can be sent to various intelligent devices with communication capabilities to fulfill some control tasks, compared to the packet's existing reference values, and tabulated for printing. These data can also be used in a process control system to handle data from large control systems like an autonomous flexible manufacturing system.

Closed-loop process control is the control of continuous-change analog quantities such as flow rate, temperature, and pressure in a closed loop. PLC technology implements closed-loop PID control of analog quantities via an analog quantity I/O module, as well as D/A and A/D conversion of analog to digital

quantities. Closed-loop process control can be accomplished using a specific PID module or a PID subroutine.

5.5 Security

People's living standards have greatly increased as the national economy has grown rapidly. They are paying more attention to their own security concerns, which leads to increased demands for product safety and reliability. As a result, security and safety control technologies are utilized in the manufacturing of electrical automation devices to assure user security in insecure situations and to avoid threats to economic property. Furthermore, the electrical automation safety system has ensured the safety of electrical automation production and injected more vitality into its future development following constant improvement.

6. Conclusion

In a nutshell, as science and technology advance, people's desire for electricity continues to rise. As a result, power companies must improve their electrical automation technology and power system operation efficiency in order to improve the electrical automation technology's practical application efficiency.

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